

Empowerment of Traditional Traders Towards Improving Local Potential-Based Welfare in South Sulawesi

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Abstract:- This type of qualitative research uses a phenomenological approach, while the results show that the concept of empowerment is needed to encourage community economic growth and independence, empowerment activities are carried out in order to meet the needs of the community, especially traditional traders, the concept of empowerment can be in the form of training, guidance accompanied by aspects of supervision, so that In its implementation, synergy is needed between all stakeholders, the concept of empowerment must start from the government, supported by the business world and the world of education, meaning that the responsibility for empowerment is not only from the government but also involves other elements.

Keywords:- Empowerment, Strategy, Traditional, Government, Policy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional markets are a form of populist economy that contributes greatly to the pillars of the economy in Indonesia. The resilience and survival of traditional markets will affect the condition of the national economy. So the government must maintain the existence of traditional markets. Traditional markets have a very strategic position for improving people's welfare because the traditional market is an important vehicle for the sale of people's economic-scale products, especially the lower middle economic community. Ministerial Regulation number 53/M-DAG/PER/12/2008 concerning The Arrangement and Development of Traditional Markets, Shopping Centers and Modern Markets explained that traditional markets are markets built and managed by the government, local governments, private sectors, state-owned enterprises and locally owned enterprises including cooperation with private enterprises with business premises in the form of shops, kiosks, los and tents owned / managed by small traders, medium, self-help or cooperative with small-scale businesses, small capital and with the process of buying and selling merchandise through bargaining.

Traditional markets as a place of business for small traders have many strategic values. Traditional markets are clearly able to provide services to the needs of low-income people. In terms of economy, the traditional market as one of

the places of money turnover which means strengthening for the micro-level economic structure, as a means of turnaround the traditional market economy proved effective in providing services to the needs of low-income people, thus creating equitable development. The traditional market has an important and strategic role in terms of labor absorption. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in February 2016 showed that the workforce in the wholesaler and retail sectors was able to absorb a workforce of 28.5 million people from the total Indonesian workforce. Labor in the wholesaler and retail sectors is in second place after the agricultural sector. Specifically for the retail sector in the traditional market itself, the Ministry of Industry and Trade noted that there are 13,450 traditional markets throughout Indonesia with 12.6 million traders serving the daily needs of almost 60% of Indonesia's population.

The existence of traditional markets has come under pressure from the rapid growth of the modern market and will affect the survival of traditional markets. Most people still depend on the existence of traditional markets. Especially for the lower middle class, still make the traditional market as an option to do buying and selling activities. As in meeting basic daily needs. But along with the rapid development of the times and the needs of the increasingly complex consumer society, the existence of traditional markets is now experiencing such a great threat. One of the competitors of the traditional market that is a threat to the traditional market is the existence of a modern market, the expansion of the modern market is getting out of control. This is seen from the development data that will attract visitors to shop in the modern market. Unfortunately, not all circles can feel the facilities in the modern market, because the modern market is more in demand by the people of Indonesia in the middle and especially the upper middle class.

A. Problem Formulation

- What is the concept of empowering traditional traders in South Sulawesi?
- What are the empowerment challenges for traditional market traders in South Sulawesi?
- What is a good and effective traditional trader empowerment strategy in South Sulawesi?

II. LIBRARY REVIEW

A. Understanding Empowerment

Empowerment has some understanding. Empowerment in English is called empowerment. Etymological empowerment comes from the word "power" which means the ability to do something or the ability to act. Getting the prefix "ber" to be "empowered" which means strength, ability, energy, have the sense (way and so on) to overcome something. Getting the prefix and suffix "pe-an" so that it becomes an empowerment that can be interpreted as an effort / process to make able to make able, make can act or do something, both attitudes and behavior Kadarisman (2012).

Sulistiyani (2004) etymologically empowerment comes from the basic word "power" which means strength or ability. Departing from this understanding, empowerment can be interpreted as a process towards power or the process of giving power (ability / strength) to those who are not yet empowered. Suhendra (2006) community empowerment is a continuous, dynamic activity, synergistically encouraging the involvement of all existing potentials evolatively with the involvement of all potentials.

Empowerment is an important step to develop weak individuals or communities because with empowerment, weak people will free themselves from adversity as according to Ali in Sukmawati (2012) which defines community empowerment as a form of participation to free themselves from mental and physical dependence. While efforts to empower the community according to Sumaryono and Kordiyana (2015) community empowerment arise because of the form of defeat and helplessness. Therefore, a model of community empowerment was developed that refers to the theory of power (power). Society only has the potential to do so and the ability of the community to be influenced that can depend on various factors, namely capacity, trust, resources and organizational context as supporters.

➤ The definition of empowerment seen from the goals, processes, and ways of suharto empowerment (2009) is as follows:

- Empowerment aims to increase the power of the weak or disadvantaged.
- Empowerment is a process by which people become strong enough to participate in various control over and influence the events and institutions that affect their lives. Empowerment emphasizes that people acquire enough skills, knowledge and power to influence their lives and the lives of others who are of concern to them.
- Empowerment refers to the effort of relocating power through changes in social structure.
- Empowerment is a way in which people, organizations and communities are directed to be able to control (rule over) their lives.

Empowerment is a process or goal. As a process, empowerment is a series of activities to strengthen the power or power of weak groups in society, including individuals experiencing poverty problems. As a goal, empowerment

refers to the circumstances or results that are to be achieved by a social change, namely a society that is empowered, has power or has knowledge and ability to meet its life needs both physical, economic, and social such as having confidence, being able to convey aspirations, having a penetcaharian eye, participating in social activities, and being independent in carrying out its life tasks.

Sulistiyani (2004) community empowerment is a learning process that takes place gradually, which includes:

- The stage of awareness and formation of behavior towards being conscious and caring so that it feels the need for increased self-capacity.
- The stage of transformation of abilities in the form of knowledge insights, skills, skills to be open to insights and provide basic skills so that they can take a role in development.
- Stage of increasing intellectual ability so that innovative initiatives and abilities are formed to usher in self-reliance.

The notion of empowerment put forward by Stewart in Priansa (2014) states that etymologically empowerment comes from the word "power" which means power, which is the ability to strive for something to happen or not at all. Empowerment according to Rukminto (2001) states that empowerment is encouraging the community to determine for themselves what he should do in relation to efforts to overcome the problems he faces. So that people have full awareness and power in shaping their future.

Jim ife in Kadarisman (2012) empowerment as an effort to provide people with resources, opportunities, knowledge, and skills to improve their ability to determine their future and to participate in and influence the lives of their communities. Ismail in Sukmawati (2012) said that empowerment is an effort to provide autonomy of authority and trust in order to complete their duties as best as possible. Furthermore, empowerment according to Mardikanto and Soebianto (2012) is a participatory process that gives confidence and opportunity to the community to review the main challenges of their development and propose activities designed to overcome the problem.

Empowerment activities can be grouped into several parts according to Koswara in Rukminto (2001) which is as follows:

➤ *Capital assistance*

One aspect faced by a helpless society is capital. The absence of capital causes people to be unable to do something for themselves and in the environment.

➤ *Infrastructure development assistance*

Efforts to encourage empowered communities then there needs to be an assistance for infrastructure development. Infrastructure in the midst of a helpless society will encourage them to explore their potential and make it easier for them to carry out their activities.

➤ *Assistance assistance*

Community assistance is necessary and important. The main task of the companion is to facilitate the process of learning or reflection and to be a mediator for the community.

➤ *Institutional*

The existence of an institution or organization in the midst of society is one of the important aspects to create empowerment. The existence of institutions will make it easier for people to coordinate, besides that they are also trained to live trained.

Sumaryadi (2005) community empowerment is an effort to prepare the community along with steps to strengthen community institutions so that they are able to realize progress, independence, and welfare in an atmosphere of sustainable social justice. Vitalaya (2000) Community Empowerment is an effort to build community capabilities and empower existing human resources through institutional development of facilities and infrastructure and the development of assistance, counseling, and implementation. Soetomo (2015) explained that there are three indicators in the community empowerment process, namely as follows:

➤ *Granting authority*

The problem that arises due to the lack of authority and participation in decision making, the solution offered is the granting of greater authority to the community including the lower layers at the community level in building management.

➤ *Capacity building*

The capacity building process is expected that the community will increasingly have high independence and not rely on one side alone. Thus, this process requires an outside role as stimuli to grow the potential and capacity of the community.

➤ *Establishment of local institutions*

The presence of local institutions is as a means that can facilitate joint actions that will increase power, because in general local people often experience helplessness that does not have the courage to convey their aspirations to the public. Therefore, for this local institution, it is as a means of making decisions from various aspirations that enter and as a means of conveying to stakeholders (government or non-governmental).

Payne (1997) empowerment can be interpreted as the process of helping people to gain the power to make decisions and determine the actions to be taken, related to themselves including reducing personal and social barriers in taking action through increased ability and confidence to use their power by transferring power from the environment. In essence, the empowerment process determines the independence of society as a result, empowerment shows to the ability of people, especially in vulnerable and weak groups so that they have the strength or ability to meet their basic needs so that they have freedom in the sense that they are not only free from hunger, free from ignorance, free from pain, reaching productive sources that allow them to increase their income and obtain the goods and services they need

and participate in the development process and the decisions that affect them. Empowerment is the provision of responsibility and authority in developing their work and making decisions.

Implementation of the process and achievement of empowerment goals through the implementation of an empowerment approach shortened to 5P, namely: settlement, strengthening, protection, support and maintenance according to Suharto (2009)

- Settlement is creating an atmosphere or climate that allows the potential of the community to develop optimally. Empowerment must be able to free the community from cultural and structural barriers that hinder.
- Strengthening is strengthening the knowledge of the ability that people have in solving problems and meeting their needs. Empowerment must be able to grow all the abilities and confidence of the community that supports their independence.
- Protection is to protect the public, especially weak groups, from being oppressed by strong groups, avoiding unbalanced competition between the strong and weak, and preventing the exploitation of strong groups against the weak. Empowerment should be directed at the elimination of all kinds of discrimination and domination that do not benefit the small people.
- Support is to provide guidance and support so that the community is able to carry out its role and life tasks. Empowerment must be able to support the community so as not to fall into a state and position that is increasingly weak and marginalized.
- Maintenance is maintaining conducive conditions so that there is still a balance of power distribution between various groups in society. Empowerment must be able to ensure harmony and balance that allows everyone to get the opportunity to strive.

Parsons in Suharto (2009) empowerment is a process by which people become strong enough to participate in various control over and influence over events and institutions that affect their lives. Empowerment emphasizes that people acquire enough skills, knowledge, and power to influence their lives and the lives of others who are of concern. Risianti in Sukmawati (2012) suggests empowerment is freeing a person from rigid control and giving that person the freedom to take responsibility for his ideas, and his decisions, as well as his actions. Sedarmayanti (2004) empowerment is to give confidence and ability to the community that they have an important role in achieving government goals. Thus, the empowerment has benefits that can be felt.

B. Empowerment Model

Khan in Priansa (2014), an empowerment model that can be developed to ensure success in the empowerment process.

➤ *Desire*

The first stage in the empowerment model is the presence of delegation and engagement. Indicators related to desire are:

- Be given the opportunity to identify problems that are developing.
- Encourage the creation of new perspectives and think about strategies in carrying out work.
- Describe the expertise of the team as well as train to supervise itself.

➤ *Trust*

After the desire of management to empower, the next step is to build trust. The existence of mutual trust will create good conditions for the exchange of information and advice. Indicators related to trust are:

- Provide opportunities to participate in policy making that applies to the empowerment process.
- Provide sufficient time and resources in completing the work.
- Provide adequate training to support the needs related to the work carried out.
- Respect differences of views and appreciate the success achieved.
- Provide access to enough information so that it will get good information.

➤ *Confident*

Trusting each other will cause confidence while respecting the abilities possessed. Indicators related to self-confidence are:

- Explore ideas and suggestions.
- Expand and build the network.
- Provide a schedule of work instructions and encourage the completion of good work.

➤ *Credibility*

Credibility is concerned with rewarding and developing a work environment capable of encouraging healthy competition. Credibility indicators relate to:

- Increased targets in all parts of the employment level.
- Introduce individual initiatives to make changes through partitioning.
- Help resolve differences in goal and priority determination.

➤ *Accountability*

The next stage in the empowerment process is community accountability on the authority granted with the aim of establishing consistently and clearly about the role, standards, and objectives about performance assessment. This stage is a means of evaluating employee performance related to the responsibilities and authorities that have been given. Indicators for accounting are:

- Provide assistance in completing the workload.
- Provide the period and time of feedback.

➤ *Communication*

The last step is open communication to create mutual understanding. This openness can be realized by criticism and suggestions. Indicators that include communication are:

- Establish an open communication door policy.
- Take time to get information and discuss the problem openly.
- Creating opportunities to get cross-competency training

Adiyoso (2009) empowerment refers to the improvement of resources as well as a process to improve the ability of society to participate, decide, control and increase the capacity of individuals in making choices with concrete actions. Thus there are seven community empowerment strategies, including:

- Increase the capacity of individuals and groups. This aspect is very important because empowerment is the process of making helpless individuals become helpless.
- Recognition and appreciation of values. This aspect is in addition to being an award for basic human rights, local values can contribute to the empowerment process.
- Diversity. Similarly, with the aspect of recognition of local values, uniform policies and recognition in carrying out community empowerment are ineffective and even contracted.
- Participation. The participation aspect is a condition of empowerment because with participation, a sense of community arises so that it can encourage to formulate and solve problems faced in a community. Participation can also unite the potential of both mind and energy in a particular community group.
- Human rights and justice. Given that empowerment is partly recognized as a process for regaining power, it is safe to interact this there must be democratic law enforcement and justice.
- Conducive environment. Empowerment also requires a conducive environment and systems and atmospheres that support the realization of empowerment.
- Partisanship. Helplessness is also caused by the "defeat" or "marginalization" of society by structures and systems, to make the community empowered then it needs a special way for this group. Therefore, there must be a temporary policy by partisanship towards community groups. Without this, efforts to increase individual capacity, uphold human rights and create a conducive environment become futile, because this society can never catch up with more empowered groups of people.

C. *Empowerment Indicator*

According to Kieffer in Suharto (2009) empowerment includes three dimensions of empowerment which refers to:

- A development process that starts from individual growth which then develops into a larger social change.
- A psychological state characterized by self-confidence, useful and able to control yourself and others.
- Liberation results from a social movement, which begins with the education and politicization of the weak and then involves the collective efforts of the weak to gain power and change the structures that are still pressing.

D. Steps in the Empowerment Process

Suharto (2009) succeeded in a process of community empowerment through the following steps:

- Every society is trained to have a high level of sensitivity to the social, economic and political developments that occur.
- Society is trained as a kind of skill in response to the needs and problems it faces, and
- Society is built to always like to work together in solving a problem.

E. Market Concept

Majid in Malano (2001) The market is a place where there is interaction between sellers and buyers, the market in which there are three elements, namely sellers, buyers and goods or services whose existence cannot be separated, the meeting between sellers and buyers causes buying and selling transactions. The market plays an important role in driving the economy of the Indonesian people in addition to being the estuary of people's products, the market also serves a place to work that means a lot to the community. Today the market is known for its traditional markets and modern markets. The existence of the traditional market is very large for most Indonesian people as a place to meet daily needs and periodic needs or clothing and food needs as well as a means of supporting the progress of the country's economy. In the traditional market there are many types of commodities that are traded usually household goods such as vegetables, groceries, clothing, and other daily necessities. Fitri (2015) states that the market is not only a exchange institution, but the market serves as a place for the spread and storage of goods and the transfer of commodities from one person to another, or from one place to another and the role of one to another.

In Ajib Rosidi (2006) the market is a collectivity of free decisions between producers and consumers. If the producer's decision is determined by alternative costs, profit expectations, and market price expectations, then consumer decisions are determined by purchasing power, income minus savings, commodity price and price expectations, as well as individual factors such as interests, needs, and so on. In connection with the description above, it is stated that the traditional market is a place where sellers and buyers meet in the social sphere of society. Not only the occurrence of the buying and selling process that is understood in terms of economics, but there is a value of collectivity (togetherness) that is manifested in the social interaction of people from various circles. There is an emotional closeness characterized by the process of bargaining, subscriptions, and even debt. This indicates a personal connection and trust that is built between each other.

➤ Traditional Market

Traditional market is a market that is managed simply with a traditional physical form that implements a direct bargaining transaction system where its main function is to serve the needs of the community both in villages, sub-districts, and others. The interesting thing about traditional markets is that traditional markets concern the lives of more people and the majority of small communities. The

implication is that traditional markets have high strategic value in maintaining the balance of regional development and controlling the wheels of alexander's economy in Fitri (2015).

Sinaga (2008) suggests that prices in this traditional market have an uncertain nature, therefore bargaining can be done. When viewed from the level of comfort, traditional markets have tended to be rundown with locations that are not neatly arranged. Buyers in traditional markets (usually mothers) have a behavior that is happy to transact by communicating / dialogue in terms of pricing, looking for the quality of goods, ordering the desired goods, and the development of other prices. Furthermore, according to Rosyidi (2006) the traditional market is currently still one of the important economic activities for some Indonesians. Various obstacles and changes that occur have marginalized traditional markets that have long had the function of redistribution of products produced by the community. Improvements in traditional market management are expected to improve competitiveness, financing efficiency and environmental management.

Based on Makassar City Regional Regulation number 15 of 2009 concerning the protection, empowerment of traditional markets and modern market arrangement article 21 paragraph (2) namely the implementation of traditional markets must meet the following conditions, as follows:

- Taking into account the socio-economic conditions of society and the existence of traditional markets, micro, small, medium enterprises, modern markets and modern stores.
- Provide facilities that ensure a clean, healthy, hygienic, safe, orderly traditional market and comfortable public space.
- Provide adequate motor vehicle and non-motorized parking facilities within the building area.
- Provide stop facilities or temporary stops of public transportation vehicles for the purpose of ups and down passengers heading to and going to the market.
- Clarity of division of business premises blocks according to the classification of types of merchandise, with the completeness and adequacy of funding systems, lighting, and air circulation both artificial and natural.
- Adequacy of the quantity and quality of public facilities, including public toilet facilities, trash cans, mushollah and other facilities.
- Availability of firefighting facilities and safety lines for officers and market users.
- Improvement of waste systems to improve the quality of cleanliness in the market

➤ Modern Market

Based on Makassar City Regional Regulation number 15 of 2009 concerning protection of protection, empowerment of traditional markets and modern market structuring article 1 paragraph (11) modern markets are markets built and managed by the Government, Private or Cooperatives in the form of shopping centers such as malls, plazas, and shopping centers and the like where the management is carried out in a modern

manner and prioritizes shopping convenience services. with management in one hand, relatively strong capital and equipped with a definite price tag.

Sinaga (2008) modern market is a market managed with modern management, generally found in urban areas, as a provider of goods and services with good quality and service to consumers who are generally members of the upper middle class society. Modern markets include malls, supermarkets, department stores, shopping centers, franchises, convenience stores, convenience markets, convenience stores and so on. Furthermore, according to Hutabarat in Arianty (2013) the modern market is not only different from traditional markets, but this type of market sellers and buyers do not transact directly but buyers see the price tag listed in the goods (barcode), different in buildings and services are carried out independently (self-service) or served by salespeople. The items sold, in addition to foodstuffs such as fruits, vegetables, meat, most of the other items sold are items that can last a long time.

Andini (2013) suggests that goods sold in the modern market have a variety of different types, in addition to providing local goods, the modern market also provides imported goods. The goods sold have a relatively more guaranteed quality because through strict selection so that goods that do not meet the classification requirements will be rejected. In terms of quantity, modern markets generally have a measurable supply of goods in warehouses. In terms of price, the modern market has a definite price tag. The modern market also provides good service with cool air conditioning, comfortable and clean atmosphere, category goods display is easy to achieve and relatively complete, product information is available through the reader machine, the presence of shopping baskets or push baskets and supported by cashiers and salespeople who work professionally.

➤ *Differences between Traditional And Modern Markets*

Andini (2013) posits a fundamental distinction between traditional markets and modern markets. The characteristics of traditional markets and modern markets include:

➤ *Characteristics of traditional markets include:*

- The process of buying and selling goods and others through the process of bargaining prices.
- The goods provided are generally kitchen and household goods.
- The price of goods sold is relatively cheap and affordable.
- Open and air-conditioned areas.
- An area that looks dirty and muddy.

➤ *The characteristics of the modern market include:*

- The price of the goods sold has been listed and given a barcode.
- The goods sold are diverse and generally durable.
- Being in the building and the service is done alone (self-service).
- Air-conditioned and comfortable room is not exposed to the hot sun.
- The place is clean.

- The layout of the place is very much considered to facilitate the search for goods.
- Payment is made by bringing the goods to the cashier and there is no bargaining anymore.

F. Merchant Concept

Trade is an activity that has the aim of delivering goods with the intention of meeting daily needs. People whose activities trade are referred to as traders. A trader is a person who trades, trading goods that are not self-produced for profit. Nikmah (2015) trader as a person / entity that conducts activities to sell goods / services in the market or is maintained by taking place to trade in certain locations that have been set. A merchant is a person who sells products or goods to consumers either directly or indirectly.

Kansil (2008) traders are those who do business deeds as a day job. Business action in general is the act of buying goods to sell again. A trader is a person who runs a business selling crafts or a small exchange business. Traders are also commonly interpreted as people with relatively varied capital who seek in the field of production and sale of goods or services to meet the needs of community groups. Traders are the most influential economic actors in the trade sector because their contribution is as a liaison of producers and consumers. The welfare of a trader can be measured by his income, therefore factors that affect the trader's income must be considered so that the trader's income is stable and welfare increases so that buying and selling activities in the market continue to run smoothly, the number of existing traders will remain and increase.

Damsar (2007) merchants are people or institutions that sell products or goods to consumers either directly or indirectly. Traders are divided into three, namely:

➤ *Wholesaler/distributor/sole agent*

A distributor is a merchant who buys or gets merchandise products from the first hand or the manufacturer directly. Large traders are usually given the authority of a certain region / region of the manufacturer.

➤ *Middle traders/agents/wholesalers*

An agent is a trader who buys or gets his merchandise from a distributor or a single agent who will usually be given a certain area of sales/trade power smaller than the distributor's fiefdom.

➤ *Retail merchants/retailers*

A retailer is a merchant who sells the goods it sells directly into the hands of the end user or consumer by unit or retail quantity. The study of the sociology of economics about traders that has been conducted by Geertz in Damsar (2007) can be concluded that traders:

- Professional traders, i.e. traders who consider trading activity to be the main and only source for the family economy.
- Semiprofessional traders, i.e. traders who recognize their activities in order to earn money, but the imposition of trade proceeds is an additional source for the family

economy. These additional degrees are different for each person and society.

- Subsistence merchants, i.e. traders who sell products or goods from the results of activities on subsistence to meet the household economy.
- Pseudo traders, are people who do trading activities because of hobbies or get a new atmosphere or fill free time. This type of trader does not expect trading activities as a means to earn money instead it is possible that he will gain losses in trading.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Types of qualitative research through phenomenological approaches.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Empowerment of Traditional Market Traders in South Sulawesi

➤ Granting authority

The granting of the authority in question is that traders are given the opportunity to process buildings that have been provided by the government. Thus, traders will experience an improvement in self-quality because market traders will continue to try to maximize their way of trading to become more profitable, then there are two indicators including (a) the utilization of market facilities and (b) the provision of a clean and safe place of business. Based on this explanation, the explanation is as follows:

- *Utilization of market facilities*

Facilities and infrastructure have a very large role in empowering market traders so that it must be managed properly, because it is not only complementary but the main thing is comfort and satisfaction so as to increase the desire to shop in traditional markets not only in modern markets.

- *Providing a clean and safe place of business*

Obtaining a clean and safe trading place is a factor that will affect the buyer's interest in the goods or services offered. In order to increase the interest of buyers to shop the government urgently needs the full support and participation of traders so that the government continues to strive to grow merchant awareness to encourage the realization of a clean and safe market.

➤ Capacity Building

- *Improving the competence of traders through training*

Improving the competence of traders through training, namely in increasingly sharp business competitions, the relevant official governments provide a training to traders because of the importance of merchant involvement in the empowerment process so that traders are first given a basis as an effort to increase their business.

- *Help with capital for traders*

Assistance regarding capital is needed in increasing business, for that of course traders need capital to increase the

business they run again. The purpose of providing capital assistance is to recommend the trader's business to be more developed which in turn is able to become a developed business and also able to compete amid the rise of the modern market.

➤ Establishment of Local Institutions

The presence of local institutions is needed because it is used as a means that can facilitate joint actions that will later increase power. With the existence of local institutions, what is the complaint of each trader in the market can be absorbed properly because of the information obtained directly from the trader concerned. The establishment of local institutions there are two indicators in it, namely (a) the formation of market managers and (b) the formation of market groups or groups, then the explanation is as follows:

- *Formation of market managers*

The formation of the market manager in question is to facilitate traders in conveying their aspirations if they need something, then each market is formed a market manager who is given responsibility in order to accommodate the aspirations of traders and then conveyed to the government so that small problems can be resolved quickly.

- *Establishment of a paguyuban or market group*

Paguyuban or market group has a very important role, namely in helping the performance of market managers. Because with the paguyuban or market group can make it easier for traders to convey various problems that occur in the market.

A. Challenges of Empowering Traditional Market Traders

➤ Low Quality of Human Resources

One of the success factors of empowerment is one of them. It is the quality factor of human resources. The better the level of quality of human resources, the closer to success of the purpose of empowerment. Despite resource quality factors Man is not the dominant factor of success. Empowerment.

Conditions in the majority of traditional markets, the majority of traders are those who have a low level of formal education, the majority of them are those who do not graduate from Junior High School (SMP), although they have quite a lot of experience in the world trade. However, of course, the level of quality of their education. directly or indirectly will affect the mindset or way they trade and serve buyers.

Traditional traders who lack knowledge or low quality of human resources, often they are not able to serve buyers and customers optimally. In fact, there are often disputes between buyers and merchants, even if a trader is able to conquer the buyer's heart with a polite and gentle style, it will increase the added value to the product or goods offered. Often this happens to traders who still lack Experience in trading, especially those who are still young, often times they are easily provoked by emotions when bargaining with

buyers who resulting in prospective buyers not buying their merchandise.

➤ *Market Facilities Are Still Lacking*

One of the things that makes buyers feel comfortable when shopping is the existence of a clean and comfortable place. In addition to the bad behavior of market visitors and by traditional market traders themselves, this is also triggered by the lack of facilities, namely trash cans.

➤ *Budget Limitations*

One of the obstacles that occurs in all government activities throughout the world. Developing countries, more specifically in Indonesia is the limitations budget. Office and Trade as the managing office of Wonokerto Market realize the importance of empowerment for traders, more specifically in the form of trainings intended for market managers and market traders that itself. However, with budget constraints, the government More directing the budget on the aspect of development only. So that aspects for improving the quality of traditional market traders through education and training cannot be realized.

B. Traditional Trader Empowerment Strategy

Empowerment strategies can be carried out individually, although in turn this strategy is still related to collectivity, in the sense of connecting the community with other sources or systems outside of him. Suharto (2009) empowerment can be done through three levels or empowerment settings: micro, mezzo, and macro.

- Micro-level. Empowerment is carried out on the community individually through guidance, counseling, stress management, crisis intervention. The main goal is to guide or train the community in carrying out the tasks of his life. This model is often referred to as a task-centered approach.
- Aras mezzo. Empowerment is carried out against a group of people.
- Empowerment is done by using groups as an intervention medium. Education and training, group dynamics, are usually used as strategies in increasing people's awareness, knowledge, skills and attitudes in order to have the ability to solve the problems they face.
- Macro level. This approach is also referred to as a large system strategy, because the target of change is directed at the broader environmental system. Policy formulation, social planning, community organizing are some of the strategies in this approach. Large systems strategies view society as having the competence to understand their own situations, and to choose and determine the right strategy to act.

V. CONCLUSION

Empowerment is needed to encourage growth and economic independence of the community, so that in its implementation it requires synergy between all stakeholders, the concept of empowerment must start from the government, supported by the business world and the world of education, meaning that the responsibility for empowerment is not only from the government but also involves other elements.

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